

Temperature ramping experiments for thermal tolerance assessment

The purpose of this protocol is to evaluate the “thermal tolerance landscape” of macroalgae species and eventually adapt it for macrofauna as well. For reference, this protocol was specifically tested on the following intertidal macroalgae species: *Ascophyllum nodosum*, *Fucus serratus*, *Fucus vesiculosus*, and *Laminaria ochroleuca*.

Introduction

Thermal stress (TS) occurs when an organism is exposed to temperatures beyond its thermal comfort zone, which is the particular range of temperatures that a species can endure without adverse impacts on its health or performance, thereby ensuring the proper functioning of physical processes. If the temperature surpasses these thermal comfort thresholds for a prolonged period, an organism may experience the impairment of vital functions, accumulation of injuries, and ultimately, death (Angilletta et al., 2009). Quantifying heat resistance has been accomplished through various methods, making it difficult to compare results across different studies. The most common measures include (i) the temperature that leads to the loss of motor function or functional collapse (known as critical thermal maximum or knockdown temperature) and (ii) the temperature at which 50% of a population succumbs to heat stress (Cooper et al., 2008).

Here, we followed recommendations by Rezende et al. (2014) to apply relatively rapid ramping conditions when conducting studies about the phenotypic variation and/or the effects of thermal acclimation to critical thermal limits. Although fast ramping rates may not always reflect ecological realism, they help to minimise the impact of uncontrolled variables in experimental settings (like acclimation or individual hardening).

Our approach aims to define the “**thermal tolerance landscape**” for different populations/species by determining their **survival probability to a given thermal stress event**, as a function of both the **duration** and **intensity** of the thermal stress experienced. The method applied here is based on the approach suggested by Rezende et al. (2014) and used by other authors (i.e. Jorgensen et al 2021).

In ectoderms, the “time-to-coma” or “time-to-dead” decreases exponentially with temperature (left-side figure from Jorgensen et al 2021). Thus, the coma or dead times can be represented as a Thermal Death Time (TDT) curve that shows the threshold relationship between temperature and time, which is exponential.

TDT curves are frequently represented with the temperature on the X-axis, but can also be plotted the other way around in a more intuitive way, where curves show heat tolerance varies with the intensity and duration of the thermal stress, and are characterised by two parameters CTmax and z, from Peralta-Maraver & Rezende (2020).

Hence, the **Thermal tolerance**, which defines the temperature at which species experience knockdown or death (T_{crit}), depends on two key parameters: the constant thermal sensitivity (z), which is suggested to be unique for each species, and the upper critical thermal limit (**CTmax**). **CTmax** is defined as the temperature that results in knockdown or death of the species at $\log_{10}.t = 0$, i.e. one single time unit (Rezende et al., 2014). The relationship between these parameters can be modelled linearly by the following equation:

$$T_{crit} = CTmax - z \cdot \log_{10} t$$

In this protocol, ramping experiments will be conducted for the different populations of the targeted species to determine the parameters z and **CTmax** for each species.

Experimental conceptual framework

In a ramp experiment, temperature is continuously increased at a fixed rate throughout different temporal intervals. Once the temperature surpasses the critical level, i.e. baseline level for thermal stress, the rate of injury in test subjects will increase exponentially over time until individuals undergo severe functional impairment and/or death (Jørgensen et al, 2021).

These combinations provide insights into the differences in thermal tolerance across test groups. To better estimate each specific thermal tolerance, we propose running 4 ramping temperature essays with different durations: 3H, 6H, 12H, and 24H.

We will use chlorophyll fluorescence with a PAM device to assess the health status of our fronds during the ramping experiments. Fluorescence measures such as quantum yield (F_v/f_m : basal fluorescence/maximum fluorescence) can provide information on the state of photosystem II and serve as a good indicator of stress in plants or algae (Maxwell & Johnson, 2000). We use F_v/f_m ratios from saturation pulses, and values are usually placed between 0 and 1; lower values (usually < 0.5 for brown seaweeds) indicate the deteriorating health of the algae as a result of the stress exposure.

To obtain proper identification of the fronds' health status, at least 3 PAM measurements per frond (with the optic fibre placed in different positions onto the frond) must be taken every time. Once yield values start to decline, the frequency measurement acquisition should increase in order to identify the critical temperature and time for each frond.

Protocol

Personnel

- 2 people are needed to comfortably perform this protocol

Sample collection

- 10 to 15 sections of algal fronds per species will be used
 - That is, for a total of 4 ramps, at least around 100 different individual samples to account for possible mortality during the laboratory adjustment phase
- 5-10 cm sections should be enough
- Only vegetative structures should be collected
 - Preferably, young apical sections of the fronds, without marks of herbivory, rot or reproductive structures

Acclimation period

- A 10-day post-sampling laboratory adjustment period is recommended
- Seawater has to be kept at a constant temperature, preferably identical to the field collection temperature
- The photoperiod has to be set in accordance with the sampling moment/season
- Acclimation tanks can be RAS or open flow-through seawater systems, with an entrance of mechanically filtered seawater

When seaweeds come from the shore, they have a "history" of past conditions. Sampled individuals could have some accumulated stress because of natural weather variability for the past few weeks. Hence, we try to homogenise all these previous conditions by keeping the seaweeds for a while under standardised conditions.

NB.- At the end of these experiments, the fronds are not expected to be able to recover from the thermal stress inflicted and should be discarded.

Equipment

- 1 Intertidal Chamber © or a similar device able to control rising temperatures in a very controlled way.
- 1 Pulse-Amplitude-Modulation (PAM) chlorophyll fluorometer (here we used a Waltz JUNIOR-PAM)
- Titanium water heaters
→ For a 3H ramping experiment starting at 16 °C and going up to 48 °C, a minimum of 1400W of heating power is recommended for a seawater volume of 79.2 litres (i.e., Intertidal Chambers).
- Aquarium air pumps, while facultative, are highly recommended
- Individual identifiers for algal fronds

Experimental setting

Experiment preparation

- ★ For this particular protocol, we are using only fully submerged conditions (i.e. no tides).
- ★ For those using “Ramping boxes”: we very strongly recommend that you test your heating power beforehand to ensure a progressive increase to the aimed temperatures. Tests should be performed at the minimal experimental duration (here 3h) by simulating an increasing temperature ramp from a $T_{min} = 16^{\circ}\text{C}$ to a $T_{max} = 48^{\circ}\text{C}$. According to our tests, a minimum of 400W of heating power is needed for a 3h ramp experiment in smaller water volumes (~15-20L).

- ★ Experiments will be performed at low-light conditions throughout the entire experimental period (see picture below). Traditionally, photosynthetic yield measurements (Fv/Fm) on seaweeds are made after a period of dark adaptation (15–30 min) to allow for the complete oxidation of PSII and the electron transport chain before a saturating pulse of light. While this is easy to do in a laboratory setting, this protocol is optimised to take nearly continuous measurements and does not include a dark adaptation period while sampling. Hence, light conditions should be low and constant.

Procedure

1. Fill in the tank with seawater (or accordingly with a 35ppt saltwater solution).
2. The initial chamber temperature programme must be set at the same temperature as the acclimation tanks.
3. Algal fronds must be individually identified before being placed in the upper section of the experimental tank.
4. Make sure the air pump is ON and placed inside the experimental section of the chamber.
5. Configure the temperature controller according to your desired temperature ramps and durations.
6. Shortly before any ramping temperature experiment begins, a set of “T0” Fv/Fm SAT measurements will be taken for each sample.
 - 3 light pulses should be made for each frond.
 - Annotate initial and final temperatures from your temperature-controlling device at the beginning and the end of each set of Fv/fm measures.

7. Further, Fv/Fm measures should be taken hourly during the experiment as the temperature rises progressively, and at least with half-hour intervals once the temperature reaches 25 °C or an Fv/Fm value inferior to 0.6 (seaweeds do not seem to show a significant damage signal below this temperature, but you should check this in your species).
 - For the shortest experiment (3H), we strongly recommend taking SAT pulse measurements as continuously as possible once the Fv/Fm values start to plunge.
 - TIP: SAT pulses can be taken directly underwater on the submerged fronds to optimise measurement frequency.
8. Optionally, the experiment can be prematurely ended once the Fv/Fm values of every sample are **null** or below the 0.01 mark for each of the measure replicates.
9. Reminder: Once the experiment is over, the fronds are not expected to be able to recover from the inflicted thermal stress and thus should be discarded.

A set of R scripts can be provided by our team to facilitate the analysis of the Fv/Fm values and estimate the corresponding break-points and death-time temperatures.

Example of expected raw results

References

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